

ARTS

OVERVIEW ON HONORED ARTIST OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN, TELMAN ABDINOV'S ARTISTIC HERITAGE

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ОБЗОР О ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОМ НАСЛЕДИИ ЗАСЛУЖЕННОГО АРТИСТА АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ ТЕЛЬМАНА АБДИНОВА

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Abstract

The article studies how the transition from realism to modernism took place in the 20th century, how the avant-garde style found its way to fine art, and how all this was embodied in Telman Abdinov's work. The styles used by the artist are determined, the idea and essence of his works are revealed. His landscape, portrait, still life and thematic paintings, as well as tapestry art, which he was engaged in at the time, are involved in the study. His paintings in abstract style are identified and analyzed.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается, как происходил переход от реализма к модернизму в XX веке, как авангардный стиль нашел свой путь в изобразительном искусстве и как все это воплотилось в творчестве Тельмана Абдинова. Определены стили, используемые художником, раскрыты идея и сущность его произведений. В исследовании участвуют его пейзажи, портреты, натюрморты и тематические картины, а также гобеленовое искусство, которым он занимался в то время. Выявлены и проанализированы его картины в абстрактном стиле.

Keywords: artist Telman Abdinov, oil painting, graphics, tapestry, avant-garde, realism, abstract style

Ключевые слова: художник Тельман Абдинов, живопись маслом, графика, гобелен, авангард, реализм, абстрактный стиль.

Since the beginning of the 20th century, many things began to change in our world, which is being updated day by day. The artists of the time already understood that it is not enough to reflect the changes in the world, new discoveries and the real image of truths, to revive them in a natural form. For this, it is necessary to find new means of artistic expression, to show them with unusual presentation of color, crazy texture, new composition structure, etc. In the 21st century, these modernistic - avant-garde tendencies are still continuing.

Avant-garde is the general name of the innovative trends that deny the classical traditions of painting. "The word "avant-garde" first appeared as a military term in the sense of "confrontation" (3). Everyone is probably thinking that how the avant-garde military term entered art. The term had a political meaning, such as revolution, from the end of the 18th century. From the 19th century to the present day, the concept of avant-garde has been developed by figures of culture in the sense of innovation, revolution, rejection of traditionalism. In art, trends directed against classical traditions have gained such a common name.

Telman Abdinov is one of the artists whose shapes and colors in his works go beyond the limits of reality - aspiring to an avant-garde style. In this regard, teacher Telman's imagination is endless and inexhaustible. In both landscapes and portraits, the artist does not try to make the chosen artistic image as close as possible to the real one. On the contrary, he easily uses the colors he feels and sees in his art. In the creative process, he freely uses his fantasy, artistic imagination, and improvisation.

Mr. Telman, who has been persistently walking on the path of creativity for 45 years, is recognized as one of the important figures in Azerbaijani fine art with more than 200 paintings and examples of decorative and applied art.

Telman Manaf oglu Abdinov was born in 1954 in the village of Kulus, Shahbuz region. The charm and exquisite nature of the place where he was born shaped the future artist itself. In 1972, he entered the Azerbaijan State Art School named after Azim Azimzade with this enthusiasm. In 1974-1976, due to military service, he went to the town of Chita, bordering on the People's Republic of China, where he was engaged in painting. Telman Abdinov, who returned to his homeland after

being demobilized from the military service, successfully completed his professional education in 1978 and returned to his native Nakhchivan.

The artist, who was awarded the honorary title of Honored Artist of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2002, was accepted as a member of the Union of Young Artists of the USSR in the early 1980s, and has been a member of the Union of Artists of Azerbaijan since 1988. "Currently, his works are preserved and displayed in many museums" (4).

Telman Abdinov's multi-faceted creative researches, which have pleased art lovers with his exhibitions organized many times in Azerbaijan and abroad, have prompted him to engage in tapestry art in addition

to graphics and painting. "Gobelin is a type of decorative-applied art that is widespread in the world and is close to the carpet art of the ancient folk culture in Azerbaijan"(1). During the 1960s and 1980s, the integration of arts took place, and this process did not bypass the tapestry. In the texture of previously flat tapestries, piles, convexity, and volume emerged (2, p. 3).

The 1970s were the period when the artist worked most productively in the tapestry field of decorative and applied art.

Nature was the main source of inspiration for teacher Telman throughout his work. Therefore, the main leitmotif in both his paintings and tapestries is nature and its elements (Fig.1).

Figure 1. "Ilandag" tapestry, mixed media, 1979

It seems that Telman Abdinov has done a lot of searching in the use of soil, style and color choice in the works "Hacha Dağ" (2008, 2012), which he worked on in different versions, and in the end he achieved his wish. In most cases, he presents his portraits not realistically, but in a unique artistic style. Nevertheless, he manages to convey to the audience who they are, what kind of character and thoughts they have.

"Fragrance of the Seasons" (2000), "Istanbul. Girl's Tower" (2000), "Three Pens" (2003), "Composition" (2003), "My Native Nakhchivan" (2005), "Dade Gorgud" (2006), "The best qualities characteristic of Telman Abdinov's creativity find their bright expression in the works "Hacha Dağ" (2008), "Summer Fragrance" (2012), "Artist's Chair" (2019), "Paradise Fruit" (2020).

Mr. Telman, who tested the collage technique applied by Javad Mirjavadov for the first time in Azerbaijani fine art, achieved an interesting effect by applying a net as a collage to the background in his thematic paintings "Travel", "Unrestful Night" (1990), "Illusion" (1995). In these works, the author brings to the fore the presentation of universal sadness in conventional plastic images that wander with sadness in the place where tragedies occurred.

If we pay attention to the works decorated with national elements, where realism and modernism alternate, "Carpet still life" (2005), "Memorial of our history" (2009), "Potter" (2012), "Carpet girl" (2018), "Let's protect our history" (2018), as well as Also, in his still lifes painted in 2000 and 2006, we can see a unique configuration of the characteristic motifs of Azerbaijani art and ethnography. In these works, color-

ful expressiveness and loyalty to national traditions attract more attention. Interest and love for native Azerbaijani motifs are reflected in his still lifes and landscapes.

In the portraits of Khalil Rza Ulutürk and Mikayil Mirza, among his graphic works, the artist expresses poetic lyrics with real lines.

Each new direction in 20th century fine art took one step further away from figurativeness than the one before it. If in earlier times they tried to make the image as close as possible to a real object, then in the middle of the 20th century, abstraction became fashionable. It even got to the point that artists tried to find a solution to such a problem in their creations: if art can describe everything, then it can also describe "nothing". That is, a work of fine art may not resemble anything. There was one condition, which was uniqueness. Experienced people will probably agree with us that it was not an easy task. This idea has been confirmed in the artistic activity of a number of world and Azerbaijani artists.

Telman Abdinov, who repeatedly tested his brush in such an abstract direction, also created "Colors that do not fit into the palette" (2004), "Dance of colors" (2005 and 2013), "Untitled" (2012), "Portrait" (2014), "Colors that do not fit into the canvas" (2014).), in his works called "Dream" (2020), guided by uniqueness, he transferred his subjective thoughts and feelings to the

canvas. He set himself the main goal of moving away from real form, perspective, plasticity, size, and external similarity, and we think he was able to achieve his goal. The decorativeness of the works, metallic paint coating and color solution do not prevent abstract images from taking a dynamic dimension. In the sense of color, open and unmistakable decoration, emotional and temperamental texture of his paintings, we see the artist's line and signature.

As a result of consistent and regular artistic activity and hard work throughout his career, Telman Abdinov has risen to the level of an artist who has managed to properly solve complex and difficult creative problems.

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